

ORGANIC FIBRE REINFORCED POLYMERIC COMPOSITES

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Specific features of high-strength fibres as reinforcing fillers are considered along with some physico-chemical aspects of developing new composites on their base in combination with thermosetting and thermoplastic matrices. The mutual effect and boundary area formation during organic fibre reinforced plastics production is discussed. It is shown that specific features of anisotropic reinforcing filler and the peculiarities of its interaction with polymeric matrix predetermine the shift of "weak" link in organic fibre reinforced plastics from boundary layers deep into the fibre. On exposure to compression, shear and tensile stresses in transversal direction weak bonds between structural elements of high-strength polymeric fibre are responsible for comparatively low strength values.

Some mechanical properties of organic fibre reinforced plastics are considered (static and long-term strength, creep, fatigue), and also the stability of mechanical dielectric properties under exposure to water and high temperatures.

The results of studying boundary area under exposure to the above-mentioned factors are given.

Based on these data, the most reasonable practical applications for organic fibre reinforced plastics are discussed. The use of organic fibre reinforced plastics as structural materials may be widened as the result of improving their mechanical properties by combining polymeric fibres with glass or carbon fibres.